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Survival Strategies And Effectiveness Of Fast Food Restaurants In Awka, Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the survival strategies on effectiveness of fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State. The objective of the study was to: To analyze the impact of differentiation strategy on effectiveness of fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State; To examine the impact of focus strategy on effectiveness of fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State. The available information from the hospitality association of Anambra state chapter is 213 restaurants of this category. In each hotel, the study targeted either the manager or deputy manger. The target population therefore was 426 persons. Given the nature of this study, since the population is not up to 1000 respondents the research will utilize the entire 426 population. Method of analysis is through structure questionnaire. The researcher employed statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) as the method of data collection. Primary sources of data were used. The study found that; Focus strategy has significant effect on survival strategies of food restaurants in Awka Anambra State (t-test, 2.128, p=002). Differentiation cost strategy has significant effect on survival strategies of food restaurants in Awka Anambra State, (t-test, 3.041, p=000). It was recommended that, Focus strategy needs to understand focus strategy as a way to improve operations and should take advantage of outsourcing tasks to experts in order to help maintain their course of action and position in the market, Some of the ways in which the restaurants are able to achieve differentiation is through maintaining quality of staff, offering a variety of services and using superior products

Keywords: survival strategies, effectiveness, fast food restaurants, differentiation strategy, focus strategy

1.1 INTRODUCTION

A major contributory area to organizational success is the development of strategies for business continuity. Organizational success in a market economy is dependent on the optimal utilization of relevant resources such as the financial resources, material resources, and human resources. It is through the combination of these resources that the attainment of the goal is achieved (Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). However, the attainment of organizational success is dependent on an organizations ability to adapt to change and be innovative. Attaining success has been the major objective of any organization be it small, medium or large in the area of profit, people and the planet but this has not always been the case of many insurance firms due to its volatile environment and the appropriateness of strategies to adopt for their survival (De Lancer, & Holzer, 2011, Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024) Survival is crucial in achieving successful entrepreneurship as long as appropriate tactics are employed. Akaeze and Akaeze (2017) asserted that the more a company stays in the market, the more successful it becomes and the less likely it is to face involuntary exits. Nigeria as a country is characterized by an unstable and turbulent business environment which in turn influences the success of insurance firms and as well marred its main objective. The success rate of a growing business in Nigeria is pegged at 20%

borne out of a lack of appropriate strategies for its survival. Ogunro (2014) attributes the survival and success of organizations to various factors; firstly technology, which translates into the organizations research and development activities, technological incentives, and the level of change associated with technology. Secondly, ecological factors which translate into contextual and environmental aspects such as climate issues and weather which affect farm and industrial related businesses (Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025).

Thirdly, Legal factors which translate into discriminatory law, consumer law, anti-trust law, employment law, safety and health law and finally economic factors which translate into interest rates, inflation rates and exchange rates. Gabriel (2015) dwells extensively on the survivability of the organization as a product of its success in surmounting identified environmental challenges and seizure of opportunities. The business to this stage has proved that it is a workable entity and has enough customers and it satisfies them sufficiently with its products and services. Long term survival of organization and not the financial performance should indicate success of the organization. Bowen, Morara, and Mureithi (2019) opine that three out of five established organizations collapse in the first five years of their establishment due to the volatile environmental conditions. Appiah, Pesakovic, and Amaria (2018) argue that many organizations have failed due to their inability to embrace strategic management in their business. In the opinion of Motwain, Mirchandani, Madan, and Gunasekaran (2008), most managers lack adequate knowledge in the areas of strategic planning techniques, methodology, and implementation.

Hörisch, Johnson, and Schaltegger (2014) also support this opinion by arguing that most organizations are confronted with varying problems that deter their success and one major cause is survival strategy, which hinders the appropriateness of suitable success. This was borne out of the fact that the majority of the insurance firms lack adequate knowledge of the positive impact of survival strategies vis-a-vis strategic planning on the survival of their businesses (Argon-Correa, Hurtado-Torres, Sharma, & García-Morales, 2018, Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, 2025). In the opinion of Kotler and Keller (2010), survival in a highly competitive service industry depends upon the creation of innovative products which can be marketed at reasonable prices. It is therefore not surprising that players in the construction Industry globally are coming up with new innovative products and services to brighten up their chances of survival in their various industries. Innovation, therefore, holds the key to surviving in a highly competitive industry (Ohanyere, Arinze, & Atueyi 2025).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In the face of increasing globalization, the effects of business-level strategies implemented are of great significance in organizations. Business-level strategies include cost leadership strategies, differentiation strategies and focus strategies. The Strategy emphasizes the importance of creating and sustaining a unique competitive advantage, focusing on core competencies, delivering value to customers, and using processes and practices to achieve strategic objectives. The environment of any business which could either be stable or turbulent determines its success or failure, but in most cases business environments are turbulent.

Rapid development in terms of information and communication technologies, competition, constant political changes can make the environment turbulent for business activities. In an attempt to survive in this kind of environment, an organization tends to consider the survival strategies that can enhance their sustainability and effectiveness. Fast food restaurants face numerous challenges when it comes to implementing effective survival strategies. Key issues include a lack of access to finance, inadequate infrastructure, inconsistent government policies, and a shortage of managerial and technical skills. Additionally, socio-economic problems like poverty, unemployment, and insecurity further complicate the situation.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine survival strategies on effectiveness of fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State. The followings are the specific objectives.

- i. To analyze the impact of differentiation strategy on effectiveness of fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State.

- ii. To examine the impact of focus strategy on effectiveness of fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State.

1.4 Hypotheses

Ho1: Differentiation strategy has no significant effect on effectiveness of fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State.

Ho2: focus strategy has no significant effect on effectiveness of fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Survival Strategy

According to Sahler and Carr (2019); Stroe, Parida and Wincent (2018) survival strategies refer to some distinct efforts, both psychological and behavioural that are often introduced by individuals or organizations to tolerate, reduce, master, minimize stressful events or maneuver their ways out of trying periods. In addition, the survival strategies are not fixated as it were, just like it is for individual personality traits (Marina, Antonio & Jose, 2018), but can be explicitly taught or learnt via modeling.

While organizations are faced with limited access to financial resources, strong managerial capabilities, technology, specialized skills and the basic infrastructures, etc they somehow create several opportunities arising from diverse ideas and the available information (Read, Song & Smit, 2019), in order to accommodate and or deal with their challenges as a form of survival strategies during such hard times (Brettel, Mauer, Engelen & Kupper, 2012). Sahler and Carr (2019) classified the survival strategies into three categories, namely avoidance (trying to be less emotionally attached to a challenge), passive survival technique (partly sensitive to a challenging occurrence) and active survival technique (totally and emotionally attached to a challenging period).

Howbeit, Sarasvathy (2011) described the survival strategies focusing on problem-solving and emotion-focused approaches. In this case, the problem- solving strategy ensures that the entrepreneur becomes actively responsible to allay the challenging situations while the emotion-focused survival strategy involves the effort to regulate emotional consequences of stressful or potentially stressful occurrences. Stroe, Parida, and Wincent (2018) observed that survival strategies refer to some distinct efforts, both psychological and behavioral, that individuals or organizations often adopt to tolerate, reduce, master, minimize stressful events, or maneuver their way out of trying periods. Therefore, to survive in an unfavorable environment, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) must adopt competitive strategies to thrive in their business environment. Adhering to a single strategy can be detrimental to the sustainability of a business. This implies that an organization must adopt a survival strategy to maintain itself in a turbulent environment (Ouma and Amborise, 2016)

2.1.2 Differentiation

Differentiation strategy involves the development of strengths that can give a firm a differential performance advantage above other competitors. Differentiation strategy is where an organization attempts to gain a competitive advantage by increasing the perceived value of their products or services relative to the perceived value of other firms' products or services. To implement these strategies successfully, organizations need to have an accurate view of the current competitive situation to persuade customers about the features of sustainable products (Pondeville, Swaen & De Rongé, 2013).

Differentiation strategy is among the generic strategic approaches in building competitive advantage. Differentiation strategies are based on providing buyers with something different or unique that makes the company's product or service distinct from that of its rivals. The fundamental assumption behind a differentiation strategy is that customers are willing to pay a higher price for a product that is distinct (or at least perceived as such) in some critical way. Superior value is created because the product is of higher quality, is technically superior in some way, comes with superior service, or has a unique appeal in some perceived way. In effect, differentiation builds a competitive advantage by making customers more loyal and less price-sensitive to a given firm's product.

2.1.3 Focus Strategy

A focus strategy based on low cost depends on there being a buyer segment whose needs are less costly to satisfy than the rest of the market. On the other hand, a focus strategy based on differentiation depends on there being a buyer segment that demands unique product attributes. In the focus strategy, a firm targets a specific segment of the market (Porter, 1996). The firm can choose to focus on a select customer group, product range, geographical area, or service line (Martin, 1999). For example, some service firms focus solely on the service customers (Stone, 1995). Focus also is based on adopting a narrow competitive scope within an industry. Focus aims at growing market share through operating in a niche market or markets either not attractive to or overlooked by, larger competitors. These niches arise from several factors including geography, buyer characteristics, and product specifications or requirements. A successful focus strategy (Porter, 1980) depends upon an industry segment large enough to have good growth potential but not of key importance to other major competitors. Market penetration or market development can be an important focus strategy. Midsize and large firms use focus-based strategies but only in conjunction with differentiation or cost leadership generic strategies.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Survival Base Theory

Herbert Spencer introduced the concept of Survival Based Theory (SBT), which posits that an organization must remain viable within its surroundings. Therefore, comprehending the environment is a key component of prosperity, as is the capacity to adapt and execute the appropriate tactics for survival. Failure to do so could result in the organization's demise among its competitors (Gathungu & Ndungi, 2018). Managers must foster innovation in both internal and external environments to ensure the organization's longevity in the face of all forms of uncertainty. It is crucial for organizations to analyze and comprehend the competitive landscape of their environment to thrive, which aids in the development of survival strategies for long-term sustainability.

2.3 Empirical Studies

Webometrics-Effect of Survival Strategy and Effectiveness				
S N	Author (s)	TOPIC	Variables	Major findings
	Phiri, Ntsieni and Maake, (2025)	reviewed analyses the survival strategies and failures of SMMEs in Africa	survival strategies and failures of SMMEs	execution of digital transformation initiatives, focused financial assistance, and strategies for long-term business continuity
	Nwokolo and Onuoha (2021)	examined the relationship between Survival Strategies and Organizational Success of Insurance Firms in Port Harcourt	Survival Strategies and Organizational Success	The study findings revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between survival strategies and organizational success
	Clement, Amah and Ofurum (2022)	investigated the relationship between survival strategies and organizational innovativeness in construction companies in Nigeria	survival strategies and organizational innovativeness	The findings further reveal a strong and positive relationship between differentiation, focus strategy, and innovativeness of construction companies
	Ismaila and Mohammed (2023)	examined the effect of Survival Strategies on Small and Medium	Survival Strategies on Small and Medium Enterprises	The results of the findings revealed that product quality strategy, service strategy, pricing strategy and income diversification strategy

	Enterprises in Ogun State.		have significant relationships with SMEs' Growth at a significance level of .05.
Adebisi and Bakare, (2019)	examined the survival strategies and sustainability of small and medium enterprises	survival strategies and sustainability of small and medium enterprises	The results reveal that there is a significant and positive relationship between survival strategies and sustainability of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria
Busari and Ogunsanwo, (2017)	examined the impact of Survival Strategies (SS) on the Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises	training on performance of employees	The result revealed a strong impact of survival strategies on SMEs performance to the total variation in SMEs performance
Ashara, (2018)	examined the survival strategies for entrepreneurs and business organizations in Nigeria	survival strategies for entrepreneurs and business organizations	The study revealed that during economic recession in Nigeria, so many entrepreneurs and business organisations went into extinction while others scaled through
Micah, Mohammed and Adeboye, (2019)	examined the survival strategies and growth of small and medium scale enterprises	survival strategies and growth of small and medium scale enterprises	Findings from the study revealed that product line diversification had no significant effect on business expansion of SMEs.
Ishaya, (2016)	appraising the survival strategies of small and medium scale businesses and their performance	survival strategies of small and medium scale businesses and their performance	It was concluded that for a business to achieve success or survive especially in a turbulent environment such as the one seen in Nigeria today, it must carefully plan with detailed appraisal for the environment it operates and adopt appropriate survival strategy to take competitive advantage so as to ensure sustainability in operation and long-term survival of the business.
Sibanda, et al. (2014)	examined employees' survival strategies in an under-performing Zimbabwean parastatal	employees' survival strategies in an under-performing Zimbabwean parastatal	Employees have resultantly resorted to alternative survival means, such as theft, fabricating leave, moonlighting, including refusal to leave company's accommodation facilities

2.4 Knowledge Gap/Summary

The struggle to survive is a natural instinct; and as postulated by Darwin (1959), “survival is a constant battle against the environment”. It is therefore natural for businesses to struggle against imminent collapse or failure amidst the contextual hostility. In the process, they deploy diverse practices to gain competitive advantage. Absurdly, these responses might not have yielded the right solution to overcome the crisis. Business researchers described the traditional business approaches as inappropriate in this scenario. Scholars such as Smallbone, Kitching and Xheneti (2009) believe that there is no single best practice that guarantees business survival, or success, and that firms adaptation and performance are contingent upon

organizational factors such as resources available, and external influences, including product, labour and capital market conditions.

In the same vein, Nguyen and Kock (2011) suggested the need for a new perspective that would enhance the understanding of how firms survive in turbulent environments. However, contemporary business scholars such as Mishra (2012) believe that the difference between survival and extinction is more about discipline versus excess; and adaptation versus rigidity. However, over the years, several problems have been identified to limit the growth, survival of various small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs). This has effectively affected their contribution of to the economic growth of Nigeria. Lack of conducive and enabling macroeconomic policy environment among other problems remains the drawback to the survival, development and growth.

Fast food restaurants are associated with constant struggle against imminent collapse due to contextual hostility that bedevils the sector. While many of them often die before their fifth anniversary, several others secure their survival by embarking on diverse practices aimed at gaining competitive advantage. Diminishing growth potentials in the economy have further drawn increased attention on the need to study survival strategies and growth of fast food restaurants in Nigeria. The study therefore assessed the impact of survival strategies on the effectiveness of Fast food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State as a study.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

Survey research design was used in carrying out the study. Ikeagwu (1997) opined that studies of this nature will be survey method to look for information on facts, attitudes, practices and opinions of the respondents.

3.2 Sources of Data

The source of data collection for this research work was derived from two specific areas, the primary and the secondary sources. In this study, the data collection technique was based on questionnaire. The researcher developed the questionnaire that will be administered to the respondents.

3.3: Population of the Study.

The study focus on classifications of restaurants described as 'eating house' within the Centra Business District of the state. The available information from the hospitality association of Anambra state chapter is 213 restaurants of this category. In each hotel, the study targeted either the manager or deputy manger. The target population therefore was 426 persons.

3.5 Sampling techniques

The research adopts two sampling techniques, namely purposive sampling and stratified sampling. Purposive sampling enables the researcher to choose the respondents that were of interest to the study while the stratified random sampling permits each of the different respondents in all the different states to be selected without bias.

3.6: Method of Data Collection.

The major research instrument adopted for the study is the uses of structured questionnaire to elicit responses for the sample population. This instrument of the collection is divided into two.

SECTION A: Deals in the bio-data of the respondent while section,

B: Deals in the question while respondents are expected to respond to, depending on their choice.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis.

In this study, the descriptive statistics such frequency counts with simple percentage were used to analyse bio-data of the respondents and the four research questions. At the inferential level of analysis, linear regression were used to test hypotheses 1 and 2 to determine the extent of correlation between x and y variables (Independent and Dependent). All analyses were done through the application of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 20 windows).

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This chapter presents the data obtained from the respondents through the administered questionnaire. Four hundred and twenty-six (426) were administered, to the selected staff. However, three hundred and seventy-seven (377) copies were retrieved.

Table 4.1 Respondent rate of the collected questionnaire

S/N			Percentage Returned
1	Copies of questionnaire Distributed	426	100
2	Copies of questionnaire Returned	396	95.2
3	Copies of questionnaire Rejected	19	0.50
	Copies of questionnaire used	377	94.3

Source: Field Survey 2025

From the table above, four hundred twenty-six (426) copies of the questionnaire were distributed. Three hundred ninety-six (396), were returned which represent 95.2, while nineteen (19) were rejected because they were not properly filled. Three hundred and seventy-seven (377) which represents 94.3% were used in the analysis.

4.2 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.2.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below

MODEL ONE

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.175 ^a	.031	.025	1.42675	.031	5.885	2	374	.003	1.617

a. Predictors: (Constant), DCS, CLS

b. Dependent Variable: EFF

Table 4.2.1 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.31%. This implies that 31% of the variation on survival strategy is explained by variations in focus strategy (FS) and differentiation cost strategy (DCS). This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.25%.

Test for autocorrelation: This is used test whether errors corresponding to different observation are uncorrelated. If the value of the durbin-watson from the regression result is close to 2 no autocorrelation in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly then there is autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 1.6 reveals no autocorrelation in the models. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.617

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.959	2	11.979	5.885	.003 ^b
	Residual	761.325	374	2.036		
	Total	785.284	376			

a. Dependent Variable: EFF

b. Predictors: (Constant), DCS, FS

The f-statistics value of 5.885 in table 4.2.2 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on independent variables such as Focus strategy (FS) and

differentiation cost strategy (DCS) can collectively explain the variations in survival strategy and effectiveness.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.582	.176		9.005	.000	1.237	1.927
	FS	.302	.142	.177	2.128	.002	.023	.581
	DCS	.227	.162	.003	3.041	.000	.326	.312

a. Dependent Variable: EFF

A’p priori Criteria: This is determined by the existing business theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the business parameter under review. In table above, we found out that focus strategy has a positive sign given its value as .302; this implies that a unit increase in focus strategy increases the employee output by 30%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. Differentiation cost strategy has a positive sign given its value as .22%; this implies that a unit increase in Differentiation cost strategy increases the employee output by 22%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation.

T- Statistics: The t-test is used to measure the individual statistical significance of our explanatory parameter in the model. From table Coefficients above focus strategy is 2.128, this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to employee output. Differentiation cost strategy is 3.041 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to employee output at 5% level of significant.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

The essence of this is to ascertain how significant are the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Differentiation cost strategy has no significant effect on effectiveness of food restaurants in Awka Anambra State.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Differentiation cost strategy variables have a t-statistics of 3.041 and a probability value of .000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Differentiation cost strategy has significant effect on effectiveness of food restaurants in Awka Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Cost focus strategy has no significant effect on effectiveness of food restaurants in Awka Anambra State

Cost focus strategy has a t-statistics of 8.433 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Cost focus strategy has no significant effect on effectiveness of food restaurants in Awka Anambra State

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Differentiation Cost Strategy and Effectiveness: The study found that Differentiation Cost Strategy has a significant positive effect on effectiveness of fast food restaurant in Awka The study found that companies: engages customers using the latest technology, introduces new products, constantly improve existing products, is fast and flexible in dealing with change and it uses qualified staff to engage customers. The study further established that companies differentiate their products from those of rivals using various strategies which include Product Differentiation which includes difference in both perception and physical appearance which can be achieved by advertising. Employees, and other associates that interact with customers can be competent, courteous, credible, reliable and responsive;

these individuals are the link between the product and the customer. If the link breaks the business will be affected and it will get destroyed. Another technique is to differentiate price. Through this technique, the company is able to maximize its potential revenue through offering each segment distinct product at a different price. This study is in line with the study of Gopalakrishna, & Subramanian, (2011), Gwangwava & Zororo (2021), Hashem Hamid & Samira (2012). who found significant effect between Differentiation Cost Strategy and Employee Output

Cost Focus Strategy and Effectiveness: The study found that Cost focus strategy has a significant positive effect on efficiency of hospitality firms in Anambra State. The study revealed that to a great extent companies; makes brand and vision visible tour niche market; makes niche specific adverts and marketing drives; train employees on the needs and mindsets of the focus market; establishes the structure of the organization that makes it possible for centrality of niche clients' decisions of the business. The study further established that company identifies the segments of the market that their business can perform best. They also provided ways through which they get to determine the segment that best suits them. One of them was through Recognizing Varying Needs of Clients and Customers based on their demographics, geographic, behaviour, and Psychographic bases (lifestyle, values, personality). The second method was analysing needs to aid in determination of the niche- it is crucial for a business to analyse the needs and wants of various markets before they determine their own niche. The study also found that Conducting Extensive Research also enables the businesses to determine the segment that will enable them become more profitable. This study is in line with the study of Hilman, (2019), Hunjra, Faisal, and Gulshion, (2017) Ibrahim (2020) who found significant effect between cost focus strategy and efficiency.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1: Summary.

The basic objective of this study is the survival strategies and effectiveness of food restaurants in Awka, Anambra State. From the analysis of the data especially, and the testing of hypothesis it was realized that:

- i. Focus strategy has significant effect on survival strategies of food restaurants in Awka Anambra State (t-test, 2.128, p=002)
- ii. Differentiation cost strategy has significant effect on survival strategies of food restaurants in Awka Anambra State, (t-test, 3.041, p=000)

5.2 Conclusion

The Survival strategy analysis effect the improvement of organizational performance. The theories that already exist about management and organization make more emphasized linkages, that the influence the competitive strategy analysis to increase organizational performance. The results of the theoretical evidence from this study can be used to solve problems that occurs the competitive strategy analysis and improvement of organizational performance. Improvement of organizational performance can be improved through increases in the survival strategy analysis. For an organization, the performance is the result of cooperation activities among member or component of the organization in order to realize the goals of the organization. Organizational performance based on the idea that the organization is a voluntary association of productive assets, including human, physical resources and capital, for the purpose of achieving common goals.

5.3 Recommendations

The following Recommendation were Raised in this Study

- i). Focus strategy needs to understand focus strategy as a way to improve operations and should take advantage of outsourcing tasks to experts in order to help maintain their course of action and position in the market,
- ii) Some of the ways in which the restaurants are able to achieve differentiation is through maintaining quality of staff, offering a variety of services and using superior products

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